

Autism and Gender Identity – School Experiences: A Review of the Literature

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Abstract

Much research has shown that there are significantly higher levels of autism diagnosis and presentation of autistic traits in the trans* community (de Vries *et al.*, 2010; Strang *et al.*, 2014; Murphy *et al.*, 2020; Warrier *et al.*, 2020), than in the wider population. Historically the focus of research pertaining to those with autism, and those with other diagnoses, has focused on rights and equality rather than on the many tangible barriers that exist in relation to gender (Paechter *et al.*, 2021) and school experiences. This paper examines the literature in relation to the school experiences of the autistic trans* and gender diverse community.

Keywords: Autistic, Trans, Gender Diverse, Non-binary, Autism, Intersectionality, School Experiences

Three Key Highlights

- There is a paucity of research in relation to autism and gender identity within the school context in the Republic of Ireland.
- Cis-heteronormative structures and systems in schools can serve to marginalise, stigmatise and exclude students who don't identify within the binary.
- Pedagogical considerations and Teacher Professional Learning (TPL) must be given due attention in relation to curricula and visibility of students with complex identities so as to support belonging.

Introduction

Historically the focus of research pertaining to those with autism, and those with other diagnoses, has focused on rights and equality rather than on the many tangible barriers that exist in relation to gender and sexuality (Paechter *et al.*, 2021). Studies that focus specifically on autism and gender identity are limited and there is space for further research into the area (Bennett and Goodall, 2016; Oien, *et al.*, 2018 and Hillier *et al.*, 2020). Autistic people report being taken less seriously when they mention they are trans* or gender diverse, as their

credibility is called into question by deficit-based understandings of autism (Strang *et al.*, 2014; Hillier *et al.*, 2020; Strang *et al.*, 2023). This paper sought to evaluate the literature relevant to the school experiences of the autistic trans* and autistic gender diverse communities. After providing guidance on key definitions and prevalence rates, this paper will examine the following themes in relation to the school experiences of autistic trans* and gender diverse learners: cis heteronormativity in schools, visibility, bullying, stigmatisation and suicidality, inclusivity labour and pedagogical considerations. These were selected on the basis of the significance of these themes as they relate to the school experiences of autistic trans and autistic non-binary students.

Definitions

Autism

Autism in its essence impacts how an individual relates to and interacts with the world in relation to social communication and the sensorial environment. Sinclair purports that autism permeates every fibre of being and influences how the person experiences the world (1993).

Trans, Non-binary and Gender Diverse

Influenced by the work of Jack Halberstam (2018), the term Trans* will be used throughout this paper to ‘open the term up to unfolding categories of being organised around but not confined to forms of gender variance’ (Halberstam, 2018, p.4). Many people identify outside of the gender binary, as neither male nor female. There are 107 gender identities currently, for the purpose of this paper the terms gender diverse, trans* and non-binary will be used.

Prevalence

In a recent study it was found that there was a 7.8% incidence of autism among participants who were gender diverse or trans* compared to a prevalence rate of 0.6 to 1% in the general population (De Vries *et al.*, 2010). This figure is purported to be even higher in a recent study by Strang *et al.*, which stated that 11% of gender diverse people are autistic (2023) and from an international perspective those who are trans* or gender diverse and have autistic traits range between 5-26% (Bruce *et al.*, 2023).

Intersectionality

The term ‘intersectionality’ was coined by Crenshaw in 1989. Intersectionality is a theoretical framework that is central to the literature relating to critical autism studies (Mallipeddi & VanDaalen, 2021). Intersectionality focuses on the many different influences that contribute to a person’s experiences, including, but not limited to, gender, sexuality, religion, socio-economic status, ethnicity, race and disability (Mallipeddi & VanDaalen, 2021). Through the use of an intersectional framework complex identities can be explored more authentically, going beyond the ‘conceptual limitations’ (Crenshaw, 1989, p. 12) of single identity perspectives. The use of intersectional frameworks allows the researcher to form an understanding of how oppressive systems and structures and the existence of systemic privilege impact the lives of individuals and groups (Moradi & Grzanka, 2017), such as those who are autistic and trans* or autistic and gender diverse.

An examination of the literature presented a number of clear themes including cis heteronormativity in schools, visibility, bullying, stigmatisation and suicidality, inclusivity labour and pedagogical considerations. Each of these themes will now be presented.

Cis-heteronormativity in Schools

Historically schools have been shaped as rigidly binary institutions (Bragg *et al.*, 2018), and binary assumptions are woven through every facet of the experience (Paechter *et al.*, 2021). Schools require parents to enrol their children within gender classifications on documentation from the outset of their schooling career, many have gendered dress codes in the form of uniforms and most have bathrooms and changing rooms that are segregated by the binary perception of gender (Davies *et al.*, 2019). The explicit and implicit communication around these spaces in schools imposes boundaries on who can and cannot use them, marginalising those students who do not fit within the binary, and further reinforcing the cis-heteronormative narrative that exists within the school setting (Kjaraan, 2019).

Many students who do not fit into the gendered stereotypes of the binary experience bullying and harassment for simply being different not only by school staff but also by their peers who perpetuate stereotypical binary roles (Brill and Pepper, 2008; Kosciw and Diaz, 2008). The lack of discussion and visibility of trans* and gender diverse people within the school curriculum and the silence that exists around them communicates to these communities that they are not accepted for who they are in the school setting (Sullivan, 2009). This is also

conveyed to cis-gendered peers through the subtleties of silence, and is compounded by school staff feeling that discussion around trans* and gender diverse identities is in some way inappropriate or sensitive and to be avoided (Blackburn and Buckley, 2005). Research has however shown that if staff and leadership engage in training in relation to supportive behaviour and the use of appropriate language this could support students in feeling safe and secure within the school environment. This could lead to better educational outcomes for these marginalised students (Jones *et al.*, 2015) as well as modelling appropriate, supportive behaviour to cis-gendered peers and creating a safe school culture for trans* and gender diverse students. Visibility as it pertains to intersectional autistic and gender diverse identities will be discussed in the next section.

Visibility

Foucault posited that visibility was, at times, a trap, another enactment of power upon the body. Beauchamp (2019) concurs with this positing that visibility of the trans* community results in further victimisation, further exclusion, more violence and more policing of gender identities. This is true of autistic students, as too much visibility can negatively impact their experience in the school setting, for example by providing highly visible supports to students, schools can make them look and feel different to their peers (Saggers *et al.*, 2011).

The problematisation of visibility and inclusion within trans* and queer theory is widely recognised (Neary and Santiago-McBride, 2021). The deconstruction of what is normative in relation to gender, the dismantling of cis-heteronormative assumptions and engagement in restructuring the traditional architecture of gender has been posited by several researchers (Spade, 2015; Halberstam, 2018), as a way to move beyond the systems that further embed gendered expectations in the trans* and gender diverse communities.

There is an implied underlying curriculum in schools that reinforces the gender binary and in turn communicates this gender binary through pedagogic practice in the education system (Paechter *et al.*, 2020). The perpetuation of the gender binary can cause young people who are trans* or gender diverse to be both visible and invisible within the school system. They are visible because they do not fit within the binary system and invisible because their gender identity is subtly yet, in ways, wholly erased by the binary system (Shuster and Lamont, 2019). Teachers sometimes recognise, acknowledge and, at times, accept trans* students, but that they find it more difficult to understand non-binary genders (Neary, 2018) making it challenging for these students to exist in the school setting. It's important to note that not all

trans* and otherwise gender diverse students are wholly out at school and this means that transphobic comments are at times, wrongly, ignored by school staff who may not be aware of a student's gender identity, this further compounds the invisibility of trans* and gender diverse students in the school system (Carlile and Paechter, 2018). Trans* people at times have to rely upon and must undertake a sense of alliance with gender norms for the purposes of survival, even though the norms do not align with who they in their essence are (Neary, 2018). Many students state that they feel unsafe to come out within their schools and they feel significant pressure to conform to the binary expectations placed on them by the system and by the expectations of others (Paechter *et al.*, 2021).

The way in which victimizing narratives are produced in relation to discourses of the protection and safety of trans* and gender diverse students, can reproduce binaries which in turn detracts from the systemic workings of cis heteronormativity (Rasmussen *et al.*, 2020). Increasing visibility often only constitutes a change in what is normative, and this has to be negotiated on the basis of shifting frontiers of acceptability, which is at its core exclusionary (Rasmussen *et al.*, 2020). Those with lived experience of being trans* or otherwise gender diverse have spoken of the intricate and complex politics of visibility and how they are subject to an inconsistent line related to gender identity or expression not being enacted in the 'right' straight way or going 'too far' at school' (Berg and Kokkonen, 2022). Constraints are placed on identity and the limits placed upon what is acceptable in relation to gender identity (Butler, 2001).

Social media has played an important role in relation to visibility and identity formation and understanding of same for trans* and gender diverse youth (Vijlbrief *et al.*, 2020). Having access to online spaces to explore identity, to research language and to self-reflect has also been highlighted as an important part of the process in the understanding of self (Bragg *et al.*, 2018). Friends (be they online or in real life) using the correct identity terms plays a significant role in relation to visibility and acceptance (Paechter *et al.*, 2021), these relationships play an important role with regard to feeling accepted and validated, leading to a more sustainable gender identity both within the school context and outside of it (Bragg *et al.*, 2018). In the section that follows literature related to bullying, stigmatisation and suicidality with regard to autistic and gender diverse identities will be presented.

Bullying, Stigmatisation and Suicidality

Due to societal oppression and stigmatisation, the dual identity of being both autistic and trans* or gender diverse has a significant impact on the well-being of the individual. Those at the intersection with this dual identity represent a significantly marginalised community and are at distinct risk for negative mental health outcomes (Bruce *et al.*, 2023). Members of this community may not feel they have the language to describe their identities due to a lack of exposure to the necessary terminology within the school setting, which proves damaging to self-esteem (Hillier *et al.*, 2020).

Those who are trans* or gender diverse are marginalised and are extremely vulnerable to victimisation, prejudice and discrimination, which places them at increased risk of physical aggression (Lombardi *et al.*, 2002). Trans* students and gender diverse students face extremely high levels of bullying, transphobic and homophobic abuse in schools when compared to other groups of marginalised students (McBride and Schubotz, 2017). Transphobic and gender identity specific bullying often takes the form of misgendering, deadnaming and stating that a nonbinary gender does not exist, students also report being referred to as 'it' rather than having their correct pronouns used (Paechter *et al.*, 2021). Deadnaming and mis-gendering purposefully without self-correction, leads to hurt, distress and feelings of being unsafe (Paechter *et al.*, 2021). This persecution can lead to poor self-confidence, loss of a sense of self and internalised transphobia (Austin and Goodman, 2016). These feelings can grow into depression and result in drug use and in many cases suicidal ideation (Clements-Nolle *et al.*, 2006).

In 2015, Irish schools were issued with procedures at both primary and post-primary level in relation to anti-bullying policies and the Department of Education (DoE) (2013) stated that all schools had to place focus on transphobic and homophobic bullying in their policy documents and also engage with educative strategies specifically related to homophobia and transphobia. However, acknowledging gender identity diversity through tackling transphobic bullying actually does not address the problem of the control that the disciplinary framework of gender places on everyone (Neary, 2018).

Autistic students often feel isolated at school and commonly experience bullying and exclusion by their peers (Cook *et al.*, 2016). Goodall (2018) found that autistic students experienced loneliness in the school setting and felt removed from their peers. Students with autism can face particular challenges with social communication, which can inhibit their

school experience in relation to peer relationships and social activities (Zakai-Mashiach, 2023) leading to depression and anxiety, which can lead to poor mental health outcomes (Culpin *et al.*, 2018). Many autistic adults report poor school experiences and increased anxiety due to bullying and a lack of understanding, on the part of their teachers and peers (Williams *et al.*, 2019). Links exist between the misconceptions of the non-autistic community in relation to autism and the poor life experiences, poor mental health, suicidality, and overall lack of well-being of autistic people (Mitchell *et al.*, 2021).

Victimisation and discrimination have been shown to directly influence the levels of distress and anxiety experienced by trans* and gender diverse people (Kosciw and Diaz, 2008). The stigma experienced by members of the trans* or gender diverse and autistic communities can place these marginalised groups at risk of increased adverse health outcomes and if intersecting identities exist this is compounded further (Költő, 2021). As limited research is available in relation to those who are both autistic and trans* or autistic and otherwise gender diverse it is difficult to discern the full impact that bullying, victimisation and stigmatisation has within the Irish context for these communities. Inclusivity labour will be addressed in the next section.

Inclusivity Labour

Many trans* and non-binary students have to educate themselves in relation to their own identities, due to the lack of appropriate education in relation to gender identity within the school setting (Paechter *et al.*, 2021). These students report that after doing the labour to educate themselves they then find themselves in the position of educating their peers, teachers and parents about gender identity in order to be understood, making it more difficult for them to come out as they are unsure if others will understand their gender identities (Paechter *et al.*, 2021). Students also felt that they had to make sure that school staff were informed as their basic needs were being ignored and transphobic and homophobic bullying behaviour was allowed to continue because staff did not realise that it was problematic (Paechter *et al.*, 2021), which diminishes the very real suffering and distress experienced by trans* people (Blondeel *et al.*, 2016; Reisner *et al.*, 2016).

Research reports that trans* students seek out safe spaces and pursue a sense of connectedness within their community to support good mental health and to bolster resilience (Zeeman *et al.*, 2017). This approach provides some shelter from the inequalities and unfavourable conditions that trans* youth can face (McBride and Neary, 2021). Reliance

upon trans* individuals to bear the weight of all the labour should be avoided, as this risks centring inclusion as individual problems to be addressed, rather than placing focus on the dismantling of cis-heteronormative systems and the removal of restrictive practices that impact all (Neary, 2018). Children and parents have a pivotal role to play in relation to setting in motion events that lead to notable change with regard to gender within the school context, which allow new perceptions of what gender can be to unfold (Neary, 2018). The final area to be considered within the confines of this paper is pedagogical considerations as they relate to autistic trans* and autistic gender diverse students.

Pedagogical Considerations

In the literature students with additional needs such as autism were found to receive inadequate relationship and sexuality education (Hillier *et al.*, 2020). The unique educational needs of trans* and non-binary youth are not fully provided for within the standard Relationships and Sexuality Education (RSE) curriculums and this can result in these students seeking information from sources that may not be accurate and can increase vulnerability (Haley *et al.*, 2020). Autistic people specifically are less likely to have the opportunity to explore their gender identity and experience greater social barriers that prevent them from learning about gender identity, sex education and relationships (Hannah and Stagg, 2016). Inclusion is an often-used word in relation to autistic students in Ireland, however an inclusive classroom can only be called such if prior and on-going training is provided to teachers (Tisdall and Riddell, 2006; Horne and Timmons, 2009; Shaw, 2019; Ainscow, 2020). Formal training in the area of autism has been found to make teachers feel more comfortable in their role and more in control of the outcomes in their classrooms, this training is recognised as an imperative component in supporting the complex needs of autistic students (McDougal, Riby and Hanley, 2020) and should be fore fronted to support staff in understanding the multi-dimensional complexities of autistic identity.

Many trans* and gender diverse youth actively seek to self-educate online and often they are more knowledgeable in relation to non-binary identities than their teachers (Carlile and Paechter, 2018). The complexity of the intersectionality of being both autistic and gender diverse further complicates access to appropriate education for these students. The enforced binary systems embedded within the school system also forces some students to drop out of particular subjects in order to remain stealth within the school setting (Neary and McBride, 2021), due to fears of being 'outed'. A focus on curricular reform is important to address the

transphobic and homophobic bullying that exists within the school system and to curb the high rates of suicidality experienced by children and youth who are trans* or gender diverse (Blow, 2009).

Subject specific issues have also been identified in the literature. Trans* and gender diverse identities have not been well considered within the arena of school sports and Physical Education leading to problematic systems, practices and approaches, or lack thereof, for these students (Sykes, 2011). Some research shows that teachers can make assumptive decisions about sporting abilities, sporting interests and capabilities based on birth assigned sex, and this reproduces binary norms (Fitzpatrick and McGlashan, 2016). Other research posits that it's not about finding gender neutral spaces, but rather about finding a space in the middle, a place where bodies are respected and assumptions around gender are challenged so that those with diverse gender identities can find a safe and accepting way to be meaningfully included (Neary and Santiago-McBride, 2021). The gender binary is deeply embedded in everyday practices within the school setting and during sports activities and PE lessons this is exacerbated for trans* and gender diverse students (Scruton, 2018). PE teachers in some studies did try to shield these students from tensions created by peers, however they did little to enact change within the system (Berg and Kokkonen, 2022).

Religious patronage still permeates the school system in Ireland. With the majority of schools in the Republic of Ireland remaining under religious patronage. In some parts of Ireland students have no option other than to attend a religious school as a non-denominational option may not be available to them. This has a significant impact for students who are gender diverse as these students often find themselves at odds and indeed targeted by the teachings and beliefs of the church. Many of the central moments in a child's primary school career focus in and around religious ceremonies, such as First Holy Communion and Confirmation. In an article from the Vatican entitled 'Male and Female He created Them: Towards a Path of Dialogue on the Question of Gender Theory in Education', it is stated that a transgender identity 'seeks to annihilate the concept of nature' (2019). With the church taking such a strong stance against gender diversity, students who are trans* or otherwise gender diverse, could feel displaced and unsupported within a religious school setting, leading to exclusion and marginalisation, which has the potential to cause serious repercussions for the well-being of the students and their mental-health (Warrier *et al.*, 2020). It is unclear if students who are both autistic and trans* or autistic and gender diverse have different experiences in schools that are non-denominational due to the paucity of research in

this area within the Republic of Ireland. To conclude a summary of the main findings of this literature review will now be presented.

Conclusion

Externally it would appear that Ireland is an accepting country that has moved beyond the bounds of its religious and conservative past, but this is a nuanced shift. There still exists a significant gap between legislative and policy reform and what is actually happening on the ground (Neary, 2018), particularly in relation to homophobia (Higgins *et al.*, 2015) and transphobia in Ireland. The anti-bullying guidelines issued to schools by the Department of Education are not adopted consistently across all schools in Ireland in relation to the stigmatisation of autistic trans* or gender diverse students, largely due to the influence of the school ethos, given that the majority of schools in Ireland are still under religious patronage (Bailey, 2017).

When considering the complex identities of students through the lens of an intersectional framework, the systemic barriers that exist within the school setting are varied and frequent. Students who are autistic and trans* or autistic and otherwise gender diverse are marginalised in a myriad of different ways that obscure their identities and neglect their complex needs. The multiple dimensions of their identities are distilled down into a 'difference', and they are made aware through the very systems that should support them, that they do not fit within the cis-heteronormative school structure. It is clear from the literature that many gaps remain in relation to the school experiences of the autistic trans* and gender diverse communities. It is worth considering that without training for management and teachers, focused and consistent pedagogical reform, and significant changes to policy, the wellbeing of autistic trans* and gender diverse students within the school setting in the Republic of Ireland is in question.

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